

Impulse Noise Removal in Digital Images by using Image Fusion Technique

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Abstract-- This technique is implemented in reducing impulse noise from the digital images and to acquire noise free image. Image fusion technique means that fusing or combination of two or more images with different or similar constraints to form a single image with all the information in each image not being strayed. Normally to reduce noise from an image we use different filtering algorithms and the outputs of those algorithms are fused together to form a perfect image without noise. In this paper we intend to use five different filtering algorithms individually to an image captured by a sensor. The outputs of those five algorithms are fused to form an image free of noise. The image obtained by using this process is of high in quality compared to the images procured by individually de noising them. The filters such as Median filter, Vector Median filter, Basic Vector Differential filter, Spatial Median filter and Modified Spatial Median filter. The above mentioned five filters are utilized to get five individual outputs which are further fused to get an image with reduced noise securing the information contained by the image. This image is further optimized to get an image with high fidelity, Edge Detection technique using canny filter is applied to the fused image to preserve the details around the edges without losing them. It is proven that using this technique has well appraised the behavior of cancellation of noise in the technique from a peculiar view point of a human.

Keywords: Impulse Noise, Image Enhancement, Image Restoration, Image Processing, Image Fusion.

I. Introduction

Order statistics filters exhibit better performance as compared to linear filters when restoring images corrupted by impulse noise. Impulse noises are short duration noises which degrade an image. They may occur during image acquisition, due to switching, sensor temperature. They may also occur due to interference in the channel and due to atmospheric disturbances during image transmission. The goal of the filtering action is to cancel noise while preserving the integrity of edge and detail information. In this paper, a novel technique for impulse noise reduction is proposed. In our technique, first an image is captured by a sensor. The captured image is converted from RGB to YIQ domain. The image is filtered in this domain with five different smoothing filters. The filtering is applied only to the chrominance (I and Q) component of YIQ domain and the filtered image is converted from YIQ into RGB domain. The denoised images obtained from five different filters are fused them to obtain a high quality image free from impulse noise.

This technique provides an immense scope in fields of military, in remote sensing, in medical application to specify the image to capture the information and also in satellite imagery to get the feeds form it with great deal of exactitude in providing the information regarding the captured space and other feeds to which it was programmed to without distortions or noise parameters encompassed in them. Due to its promising results and accuracy it is supposedly meant to be a better functionality proposed to negate the noise and nab the information which the image tends to portray to us

Impulse noise is independent and uncorrelated to the image pixels and is randomly distributed over the image. For an impulse noise corrupted image all the image pixels are not noisy, a number of image pixels will be noisy and the rest of pixels will be noise free. There are different types of impulse noise namely salt and pepper type of noise and random valued impulse noise. In salt and pepper type of noise the noisy pixels take either salt value (gray level - 225) or pepper value (grey level -0) and it appears as black and white spots on the images. In case of random valued impulse noise, noise can take any gray level value from zero to 225. In this case also noise is randomly distributed over the entire image and probability of occurrence of any gray level value as noise will be same.

II. Proposed System

In proposed system image fusion technique is used to remove the impulse noise from the digital images. Image

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fusion technique is the process of fusing the different images to one image without loss of data and for high quality. Five different filtering algorithms are used for filtering. The image from sensor is sent to these five filters at a time as input and the outputs of the each of five filters are noise free images those are fused to a single image for better appraise of the image canny filter is used and finally the output is noise free image. The five filter algorithms used for filtering are:

- a. Median filter
- b. Vector median filter
- c. Basic directional vector filter
- d. Spatial median filter
- e. Modified spatial median filter

The image fusion technique method is represented as shown below and here R^1, R^2, R^3, R^4, R^5 are the outputs of the five filters.

Figure 3.1: Block Diagram of Image Fusion.

2.1 Median filter

Median filters are statistical non-linear filters [5] that are often described in the spatial domain. A median filter smoothens the image by utilizing the median of the neighborhood. Median filter performs the following tasks to find each pixel value in the processed image: All pixels in the neighborhood of the pixel in the original image which are identified by the mask are stored in the ascending (or) descending order. The median of the stored value is computed and is chosen as the pixel value for the processed image.

2.2 Calculation of Median Value

Median value is calculated by eliminating the pixel values which are very different from their neighboring pixels. By eliminating the effect of such odd pixels, the values are assigned to the pixels that are representative of the values of the typical neighboring pixels in the original image. The median value of the marked pixel is computed as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 5 & 7 \\ 2 & 4 & 6 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Step 1: First, the pixel values are arranged in ascending order as follows:

$$1 \ 1 \ 2 \ 2 \ 3 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7$$

Step 2: The median value of the ordered pixel is computed as follows:

$$1 \ 1 \ 2 \ 2 \ 3 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7$$

————— —————

The median value is computed to be 3. Then, the original pixel value of 4 will be replaced by the computed median value of 3.

$$\begin{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 5 & 7 \\ 2 & 4 & 6 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \longrightarrow & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 5 & 7 \\ 2 & 3 & 6 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \text{Original image data} & & \text{After median filtering} \end{matrix}$$

Let the input image is given in the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} 18 & 22 & 33 & 25 & 32 & 24 \\ 34 & 128 & 24 & 172 & 26 & 23 \\ 22 & 19 & 32 & 31 & 28 & 26 \end{pmatrix}$$

Here the goal is to compute the median values of the marked pixels and replace the pixels 128, 24, 172 and 26 by their median values of the neighborhood defined by the mask. The mask to be used is a 3 x 3 mask.

Step I: To compute the median value of the marked pixel 128.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 18 & 22 & 33 & 25 & 32 & 24 \\ 34 & 128 & 24 & 172 & 26 & 23 \\ 22 & 19 & 32 & 31 & 28 & 26 \end{pmatrix}$$

Step 1a: The nine neighbors of the marked pixel '128' are now arranged in ascending order as follows:

$$18 \ 19 \ 22 \ 22 \ 24 \ 32 \ 33 \ 34 \ 128$$

Step 1b: The median value is computed as 24.

$$18 \ 19 \ 22 \ 22 \ 24 \ 32 \ 33 \ 34 \ 128$$

Step 3: To compute the median value of the marked pixel 172

Step 3a: Arrange the pixels in the neighborhood of 172 in the ascending order.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 18 & 22 & 33 & 25 & 32 & 24 \\ 34 & 128 & 24 & 172 & 26 & 23 \\ 22 & 19 & 32 & 31 & 28 & 26 \end{pmatrix}$$

After arranging the pixel values in the neighborhood in the ascending order, we have

$$24 \ 25 \ 26 \ 28 \ 31 \ 32 \ 33 \ 172$$

Step 3b: The median value is computed as 31

$$\underline{24} \ \underline{25} \ \underline{26} \ \underline{28} \ \underline{31} \ \underline{32} \ \underline{33} \ \underline{172}$$

Step 4: To compute the median value of the marked pixel 26

$$\begin{pmatrix} 18 & 22 & 33 & 25 & 32 & 24 \\ 34 & 128 & 24 & 172 & 26 & 23 \\ 22 & 19 & 32 & 31 & 28 & 26 \end{pmatrix}$$

Step 4a: Arrange the pixels in the neighborhood of 26 in the ascending order:

After arranging the pixel values in the neighborhood in the ascending order, we have

$$23 \ 24 \ 25 \ 26 \ 28 \ 31 \ 32 \ 172$$

Step 4b: The median value is computed as 26.

$$23 \ 24 \ 25 \ 26 \ 26 \ 28 \ 31 \ 32 \ 172$$

The original pixel values and the values replaced by their median are shown below

From the above illustration it is clear that the pixel value '128' is replaced by the median value 24 and the pixel value '172' is replaced by the median value 31. Here, the values 128 and 172 are entirely different from their neighboring pixels. When we take the median value, the pixel values which are very different from their neighboring pixels are replaced by a value equal to the neighboring pixel value. Hence, a median filter is capable of reducing salt-and-pepper noise. Here, salt corresponds to the maximum gray value (white) and pepper corresponds to the minimum gray value (black). Random occurrence of black and white pixels in an image is generally termed 'salt-and-pepper' noise. A median filter is an effective tool to minimize salt-and-pepper noise. And is given by

$$\text{MEDIANFILTER}(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \text{MEDIAN}(kx_1k_2, \dots, kx_Nk_2) \quad (3.1)$$

2.3 Image Fusion

Need of Image Fusion

Image fusion is expected to play an important role in future due to the availability of inexpensive hardware. Often, a single sensor cannot produce better interpretation of the captured scene. Therefore, diverse images of the same scene received from dissimilar image sensors are fused into a composite image [10]. The need for image fusion is emphasized due to the following advantages:

Overall uncertainty gets reduced because of using multiple sensors which provide redundant information and hence, this results in an increased accuracy of fused image.

2.4 Image Fusion techniques

Nowadays, there is an increased affordability of imaging sensors, which has made a hallmark in multi sensor vision system. The modalities of different sensors operating across different bands of electromagnetic spectrum can be combined resulting in an increased information content of the scene. Through the careful selection of complementary sensor modalities, the potential for significantly enhancing the information content in a simple image may be realized, by image fusion. But here we considered only either the minimum and maximum methods for the process of image fusion.

Fig. 3.3. Image Fusion Process.

2.5 Canny filter

The Canny operator (Canny, 1986) was designed to be an optimal edge detector. It takes as input a grayscale image, and produces as output an image showing the positions of tracked intensity discontinuities. Different stages of Canny Edge Detection are

- a. Noise reduction: Raw image is convolved with a Gaussian filter.
- b. The Canny algorithm basically finds edges where the gray scale intensity of the image changes the most.

These areas are found by determining gradients of the image. Gradients at each pixel in the smoothed image are determined by applying what is known as the Sobel-operator. First step is to approximate the gradient in the x and y-direction respectively by applying the kernels shown in figure below:

$$C_x = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \qquad C_y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -2 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3.4: Shows two kernels used in Canny Edge Detector.

The gradient magnitudes (also known as the edge strengths) can then be determined as a Euclidean distance measure by applying the law of Pythagoras as shown in Equation (3.6). It is sometimes simplified by applying Manhattan distance measure as shown in Equation (3.7) to reduce the computational complexity.

$$G = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2} \quad (3.6)$$

Where G_x and G_y are the gradients in the x- and y-directions respectively. An image of the gradient magnitudes often indicates the edges quite clearly. However, the edges are typically broad and thus do not indicate exactly where the edges are.

The direction of the edges must be determined and stored as shown in Equation (3.8).

$$\theta = \arctan \left(\frac{G_y}{G_x} \right) \quad (3.8)$$

1. Non-maximum suppression
 - a. A search is carried out to determine if the gradient magnitude assumes a local maximum in the gradient direction
 - b. From this stage, referred to as non-maximum suppression, a set of edge points in the form of a binary image are obtained
 - c. Output of this stage is sometimes referred to as “thin edges”
 - d. Large threshold: gives true edges
 - e. Small threshold: gives false edges
2. Tracing edges through the image and hysteresis thresholding

Canny algorithm does not use same threshold for whole image. It does thresholding with hysteresis.

- a. Thresholding with hysteresis requires
 - a. Two thresholds – high and low.
 - b. Therefore we begin by applying a high threshold.
- b. These marks out the edges we can be fairly sure are genuine.
- c. Starting from these, using the directional information derived earlier, edges can be traced through the image.
- d. While tracing an edge, we apply the lower threshold, allowing us to trace faint sections of edges as long as we find a starting point.

Usually, the upper tracking threshold can be set quite high and the lower threshold quite low for good results. Setting the lower threshold too high will cause noisy edges to break up. Setting the upper threshold too low increases the number of spurious and undesirable edge fragments appearing in the output.

III. Simulation Results

3.1 Median Filter

For Median filter, the balloon image is given as input shown in the Fig. 4.1. To the input during processing some noise is added as shown in the Fig. 4.2.

Fig. 3.1. Input of the Median filter

Fig. 3.2. Noisy Image.

Fig. 3.3. Output of Median Filter

Parameter	Value
MSF	273.32
PSNR	23.75
SNR	13.58

Table 3.1. Parameters of Median Filter.

After processing, we get the output of the Median filter as shown in Fig. 3.3. And also the Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to-Noise ratio parameters are been calculated.

The parameters, Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to- Noise ratio are shown in Table 3.1.

3.2 Vector Median Filter

For Vector median filter, the balloon image is given as input shown in the Fig. 3.5.

After processing, we get the output of the Vector Median filter as shown in Fig. 3.6.

Figure.3.6. output of the Vector Median filter

And also we get the Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to- Noise ratio parameters are shown in Table 3.2.

Parameter	Value
MSF	1284 5.2
PSNR	7.03
SNR	1.15

Table 3.2. Parameters of Vector Median Filter.

3.3 Basic Vector Directional Filter

For Basic Vector Directional filter technique, the balloon image is given as input. During processing, some noise is added. The noisy image is shown in fig 3.7.

Fig.3.7. Noisy Image.

After processing, we get the output of the Basic Vector Directional filter as shown in fig. 3.8.

Fig.3.8. Output of Basic Vector Directional Filter.

And also the Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to-Noise ratio parameters are been calculated as shown in Table 4.3.

Table 3.3. Parameters of Basic Vector Directional Filter.

Parameter	Value
MSF	16613.73
PSNR	-42.21
SNR	0.0189

3.4 Spatial Median Filter

For Spatial Median filter, the balloon image is given as input shown in the fig3.9.

During processing, some noise is added. The noisy image is shown in fig 4.11.

Fig.3.9. Input of Spatial Median Filter.

Fig. 3.11. Noisy Image.

After processing, we get the output of the Spatial Median filter as shown in fig. 3.12.

Fig. 3.12. Output of Spatial Median Filter.

And also Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to-Noise ratio parameters are calculated as shown in Table 4.4.

Table. 4.4. Parameters of Spatial Median Filter.

Parameter	Value
MSF	11379.75
PSNR	7.5695
SNR	1.6651

3.5 Modified Spatial Median Filter

For Modified Spatial Median filter technique, the balloon image is given as input shown in the fig 3.13. During processing, some noise is added. The noisy image is shown in fig 3.14.

Fig. 3.13. Noisy Image.

After processing, we get the output of the Modified Spatial Median filter as shown in Fig. 3.14.

Fig. 3.14. Output of Modified Spatial Median Filter.

And also we get the Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to- Noise ratio parameters are calculated as shown in Table 4.5.

Parameter	Value
MSF	18733.72
PSNR	-42.726
SNR	-0.5085

Table 3.15. Parameters of Modified Spatial Median Filter.

3.6 Image Fusion

For Image Fusion technique, the balloon image is given as the single input to all the five filters at a time and the output of each filter that are R^1 , R^2 , R^3 , R^4 , R^5 these five filter outputs are given to the Image Fusion at a time shown in the Fig. 4.13.

Parameter	Value
MSF	60766.92
PSNR	-47.84
SNR	-1.86

And also we get the Mean Square Error, Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio and the Signal-to- Noise ratio parameters are calculated as shown in Table 4.5.

3.7 Canny Filter

For Canny Filter, the balloon image is given as input shown in the Fig. 4.16.

Fig. 3.16. Input of canny filter.

After processing, we get the output of the Canny Filter as shown in Fig. 3.17.

Fig. 4.17. Output of Canny Filter.

Image Fusion is the technique in which a effective high quality image is obtained when a uncorrupted image is given as input. The parameters such as MSE, SNR, PSNR are also calculated and compared to itself which reduced the MSE value

Conclusion

With the exponential evolution in computations and advancements in technologies many new and sophisticated imaging techniques have been emerged. Though they prove out to best in class techniques for the removal of noise, they come with certain limitations. These new techniques tend to have bounds of their own which cannot

be neglected that easily. We aim to create a new technique that bridges the gap between the clear image and a distorted image by emphasizing the information and enhancing the distorted image breaking past the limits of those techniques by alternating and combining those techniques with other turning the disadvantages of one technique into advantages of other emulating one another giving rise to a perfect image for this we have done a brief study about the functionalities of the techniques used to remove noise. For this we in our project to remove impulse noise from digital images without loss of information in the picture by individually de noising the noised image using several filtering techniques.

Future Scope

This method can be utilized to remove noise elements from video.

This method can be used to enhance satellite images which are noised at the time of transmission to earth due to poor reception of network or due to poor transmission parameters. It is so much helpful in the field of remote sensing.

This method of fusing the images can be used in medical field in fusing CT scan and MRI scan images for better understanding of the situation to diagnose better and efficiently to provide quality treatment with low cost efficiency.

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